

**Classifying the Directory of Open Access Journals Using the Canadian Research and
Development Classification System: Analysis and recommendations.**

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This report seeks to evaluate if the Canadian Research and Development Classification (CRDC) system could potentially replace the Directory of Open Access Journal's (DOAJ) current classification model. The DOAJ currently uses a condensed version of the Library of Congress Classification system (LCC, 2012 edition) and they are seeking a replacement that is modern, global, multidisciplinary, and user-friendly.

This report includes both an environmental scan and data analysis in order to examine the CRDC and compare it to the needs outlined by the DOAJ for a new classification system. As the CRDC was only released in 2020, our environmental scan focuses on government sources to better understand the CRDC system. In our data analysis, we compared the LCC classes currently used to classify journals in the DOAJ with the CRDC Field of Research (FOR) classes, assessed their compatibility, and undertook a process of mapping those LCC classifications onto appropriate CRDC classifications. We also evaluated how some classifications and structures of the CRDC may need to be expanded in order to be used by the DOAJ. This report examines the CRDC in detail and proposes that it could be used by the DOAJ in a modified form as a replacement for the LCC system currently in use.

Introduction to the DOAJ

The DOAJ is an independent, non-profit organization that operates an index of open access journals. They accept scholarly journals from around the world on any topic and focus on international reach with team members, ambassadors, and volunteers located in 45 countries around the world, who speak over 36 languages. The DOAJ states that their mission is to increase "the visibility, accessibility, reputation, usage and impact of quality, peer-reviewed, open access scholarly research journals globally, regardless of discipline, geography or language" (Directory of Open Access Journals, DOAJ, 2022b). The DOAJ requires that all

journals that apply to be a part of their index are open access, meaning they allow for immediate free access to their articles. Journals should be active publishers of scholarly research, putting out at least five research articles annually. Additionally, journals who are submitting should have a primary audience of researchers or practitioners, but are not limited to a specific research domain, as the DOAJ wants to include a broad range of research in their database (DOAJ, 2022e). Overall, the DOAJ strives to provide open access to a wide variety of material from academic journal publishers to comply with best practices in open access publishing. They hope to attract both high quality journals and scholars who are looking for a dependable database. The DOAJ wants to give journals a place where they can gain a good reputation, comply with best standards and practice in open access, and become more easily discovered by researchers from around the world. (DOAJ, 2022c).

Journals are currently classified in the DOAJ using a truncated version of the 2012 edition of the Library of Congress Classification (LCC) system. LCC is divided into 21 subject headings, which are then divided into subtopics which are used to describe more specific topics. Each subject, at the broadest level, is assigned a letter of the alphabet, and subtopics are represented using numbers between one and four digits (The Library of Congress, LCC, 2014), which comprises the notation of the classified item. The DOAJ has at least 18,684 journals, spanning 80 languages and 130 countries currently classified under LCC (DOAJ, 2022a).

The DOAJ uses all 21 LCC headings to sort their journals, as is demonstrated in Figures 1 and 2, which were created using metadata retrieved from the DOAJ.¹ The metadata from the DOAJ used in this report was retrieved and analyzed on September 28th, 2022, and so may not

¹ *Note.* Data retrieved from Department of Open Access Journals. (2022d). *Public Data Dump*. [Data set]. <https://doaj.org/docs/public-data-dump/>.

reflect the full current collection of the DOAJ. Most journals hosted by DOAJ are under the headings for *Medicine*, *Science*, *Social Sciences*, and *Technology*; however smaller sections including *General Works and Bibliography*, *Library Science*, *Information Resources (General)* also have a fair number of articles classified under them. Figures 1 and 2 outline the number of DOAJ journals classified under each LCC heading.

Figure 1

Number of DOAJ Journals Indexed per LCC Main Class

Note. A graph depicting the spread of DOAJ articles using the LCC system (Haustein, 2022a).

Figure 2*Number of DOAJ Articles Classed Under LCC Headings*

Main class	Main class title	Number of journals in DOAJ	% of journals in DOAJ
R	Medicine	4,927	26.9%
H	Social Sciences	4,154	22.7%
Q	Science	3,305	18.1%
T	Technology	2,771	15.1%
L	Education	2,167	11.8%
P	Language and Literature	2,100	11.5%
B	Philosophy. Psychology. Religion	1,457	8.0%
G	Geography. Anthropology. Recreation	1,377	7.5%
S	Agriculture	971	5.3%
K	Law	895	4.9%
J	Political Science	704	3.8%
N	Fine Arts	697	3.8%
D	World History and History of Europe, Asia, Africa, Australia, New Zealand, etc.	627	3.4%
A	General Works	372	2.0%
C	Auxiliary Sciences of History	214	1.2%
Z	Bibliography. Library Science. Information Resources (General)	190	1.0%
E-F	History of the Americas	164	0.9%
M	Music and Books on Music	95	0.5%
U	Military Science	49	0.3%
V	Naval Science	32	0.2%
all journals		18,293	100.0%

Note. A table showing the number of DOAJ articles currently divided under LCC headings (Haustein, 2022a).

However, the LCC is currently too limited for effective use by the DOAJ. The headings are outdated, too US-centric in focus, and do not allow for enough granularity to properly

categorize the growing collection of journals by the DOAJ. The LCC headings do not always cover emerging topics. For example, the *Military Science* and *Naval Science* sections are too specific to be of much use for the DOAJ. Additionally, broader sections like *Philosophy*, *Psychology*, *Religion* do not reflect modern divisions of research. Additionally, the LCC groups most international history together, whereas the DOAJ strives to show the breadth of international research without limiting it to only one class.

The Operations Manager of the DOAJ, Dominic Mitchell, highlighted some key needs for a potential new system. The DOAJ requested the following criteria for a new system:

- Easy for humans to use both when classifying journals and looking for them.
- Easy for machines to use when processing metadata.
- Reflects the DOAJ's international and multilingual perspective.
- Adaptable and has the potential to be extended.
- Open-source.
- Compatible with the current LCC system (i.e., easy to migrate) (Haustein, 2022b).

This report seeks to assess the CRDC FOR system based on the DOAJ's needs and analyse whether the CRDC is better suited to the DOAJ than the LCC.

What is the CRDC?

The Canadian Research and Development Classification system was created in 2020 to assist in the measurement and analysis of research and experimental development being undertaken in Canada. It was developed by the joint efforts of Canadian research groups and grant agencies in response to the Canadian Federal Government's 2017 report, *Advisory Panel for the Review of Federal Support for Fundamental Science*, which recommended a closer collaboration of federal research granting agencies (Legendre, 2019). Groups involved included

the Canadian Foundation for Innovation (CFI), the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC), and Statistics Canada (STC) (Statistics Canada, 2020a). The research classified within the CRDC is intended to be useful to a variety of groups, including “governments, educational institutions, international organisations, scientific, professional or business organisations and enterprises, community groups and private individuals in Canada” (Statistics Canada, 2020a).

The CRDC was developed in consultation with Canadian academic organisations, research organisations, experts in specific fields, as well as major users of research information (Statistics Canada, 2020a). Before the CRDC was developed, Canadian funding agencies were using different research classification systems, which often only covered the mandate of a specific agency (Statistics Canada, 2020a). The developers of the CRDC intended to create a common research and development related language that could be used across the higher education, public, and government research sectors. This standardisation would allow for multidisciplinary cooperation and collaboration, which in turn would encourage better identification of emerging fields, the ability to identify gaps and strengths, more accurate and comprehensive reporting of Canada’s research and science enterprises, increased data quality, and a more streamlined operational process within the research granting agencies, especially as relates to peer review and recruitment (Legendre, 2019).

As part of their consultation process, the agencies involved with the development of the CRDC conducted seminars and public consultations to create a system which would be widely accepted as the national standard for classification of research and development projects in Canada. Over a period of 19 months (February 2018 – October 2019), the project developers

sought the input of a variety of qualified professionals, including the Australian Bureau of Statistics; Statistics New Zealand; the Australian Research Council; internal staff at each Canadian federal research granting agency; subject-matter experts; and targeted stakeholders, such as federal science-based departments and agencies, provincial funding agencies, and provincial statistical agencies. Research was conducted via webinars, online consultations, notices of interest, and invitations to comment or make suggestions. Based on feedback received during the consultation, the project developers implemented a number of modifications, resulting in the current model of the CRDC (Statistics Canada, 2020b). The graph below describes the results of the consultation and which divisions of the CRDC received the most feedback from stakeholders.

Figure 3

CRDC Open Online Consultation

- 817 responses received
- 313 responses with comments on field of research
- 5% of respondents identified their field of research as "other"

Note. This pie chart describes participants in the CRDC's open online consultations (Statistics Canada, 2020b).

Further development of the CRDC continued by referencing standards and practices which were already in place for classification systems. The CRDC is compliant with the essential components of a statistical classification as defined by the UN Statistical Commission. Namely, it has a consistent conceptual basis; is flat or hierarchical; has mutually exclusive, exhaustive categories; clearly defines the content of each category; is up to date and relevant; is sufficiently robust to ensure longevity; meets intended users' needs; provides comparability over time and between collections (interoperability); and provides guidelines for coding and output of collected data (Legendre, 2019). The CRDC was also influenced by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), *Frascati Manual 2015*, and the Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) as guiding tools. While these tools are not examined in this paper, they may be useful as a point of reference for some underlying concepts (Statistics Canada, 2020a).

The CRDC was designed with a focus on research and development projects in Canada. Statistics Canada defines research and development (R&D) using the OECD Standard from the 2015 *Frascati Manual*. Under this standard, R&D is comprised of “creative work undertaken on a systematic basis in order to increase the stock of knowledge, including knowledge of human, culture, society and environment, and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications” (Statistics Canada, 2020a). R&D must be original work, which produces new knowledge, new or improved materials, products, devices, processes or services (Statistics Canada, 2020a).

The financial element of the CRDC system is also worth noting. The CRDC was intended for use by major Canadian research fund granting agencies, and there is a considerable financial

component involved in its creation. The federal government's *What We Heard* document on the project notes that:

Research stakeholders, the government and the public are seeking information about which areas of research are receiving support and the levels of investment in each of these areas...and [to]benchmark investments and performance both nationally and internationally...The CRDC will help ensure the consistent compatibility and comparability of statistics across research funding agencies both in Canada and internationally while balancing the needs of different users and highlighting specific areas of Canadian research strength. (Statistics Canada, 2020b)

Additionally, the CRDC is intended to be updated often. Statistics Canada and other funding agencies intend to conduct minor revisions to the system every year or two, and major revisions every five years. There is a revision scheduled within the first two years of its creation, meaning there will likely be a revision published this year. The CRDC will also publish any correspondence between new versions and older versions when changes are made. This will allow revisions to be clearly followed, as well as any influence from any other systems which may have been incorporated into the CRDC (Statistics Canada, 2020a).

Structure of the CRDC

The CRDC consists of three main classifications, Type of Activity (TOA), Fields of Research (FOR), and Socio-economic Objective (SEO). Type of Activity (TOA) is used to categorise research projects by the type of research effort and consists of three possible divisions. The type of activity is classified as either Basic Research, which seeks to acquire foundational knowledge with no particular application in mind; Applied Research, which seeks to gain new knowledge towards a specific aim; or Experimental Development, which draws on previous

knowledge to create or improve new products or processes (Legendre, 2019). Field of Research (FOR) is used to categorize research projects according to the type of research they describe and organizes research papers based on which knowledge sources, objects of interest, and methods and techniques are described in them. Socio-economic Objective (SEO) is used to classify research projects based on the purpose or outcome of the research (Statistics Canada, 2020a). For the purposes of this study, we used the FOR classifications as it was the most expansive classification offered by the CRDC and its focus is similar to that of the LCC.

FOR is divided into four hierarchical levels: Divisions, Groups, Classes, and Subclasses, in descending order of specificity. Divisions are the broadest level of classification and have six possible categories. Groups are the next level of classification, of which there are 42. There are 168 Classes, and then 1663 Subclasses. Each Division, Group, Class, or Subclass is represented by an alpha-numerical code, including the RDF designation. Divisions are represented by a 5-character code, each Group has a 6-character code, each Class has an 8-character code, and each Subclass has a 10-character code. Groups included under each Division share the same broad methodology, knowledge domain, or perspective. Each Group is made up of a collection of classes which are also related to that topic. Subclasses allow for more specificity and express the most granular of descriptions. Each set of Subclasses under any given Class also contains a “not elsewhere classified (n.e.c.)” classification. The CRDC uses the "n.e.c" Subclass for anything which falls under a particular Class but does not have an equivalent Subclass listed. (Statistics Canada, 2020a).

Figure 4*CRDC Field of Research*

Level	Level Name	Number of digits (truncated – Full codes are alphanumerical and start RDF)	Count
1	Division	2	6
2	Group	3	43
3	Class	5	168
4	Subclass (Field)	7	1663
Total	n/a	n/a	1880

Note. An example of FOR structure with number of each Division, Group, Class and Subclass, and the number of digits in their alphanumeric code. (Statistics Canada, 2022b).

Figure 5*CRDC Field of Research Structure*

Level	Code	Description
Division	RDF10	Natural sciences
Group	RDF101	Mathematics and statistics
Class	RDF10101	Pure Mathematics
Subclass (Field)	RDF1010101	Algebra

Note. An example of FOR structure. (Statistics Canada, 2022b).

The CRDC FOR consists of six Divisions: *Natural sciences; Engineering and technology; Medical, health and life sciences; Agricultural and veterinary sciences; Social sciences; and Humanities and the arts* (Statistics Canada, 2022a). Each of these Divisions consists of multiple Classes and Subclasses, providing a broad depth of potential classifications within a variety of areas of research. However, some of these Groups or Classes are broader than

others. The Division of *Natural sciences* has seven Groups, each with multiple Classes and Subclasses. Meanwhile, *Engineering and technology* has twelve groups, *Medical health and life sciences* has five Groups, *Agriculture and veterinary sciences* has five Groups, *Social sciences* has nine Groups and *Humanities and the arts* has five Groups (Statistics Canada, 2020). While the number of Groups each Division has are mostly comparable, the *Natural sciences* and *Engineering* fields tend to focus on Groups and Classes of a very specific nature, while the *Humanities* and *Social sciences* cover broader topics.

Evaluation

Mapping the LCC to the CRDC System

Method

Our goal during the mapping process was to compare the LCC to the CRDC by migrating the LCC to the CRDC with as close-as-possible equivalent classifications. The datasets for the LCC classification structure and the FOR classification structure were placed into Excel to compare the two and map the CRDC classifications onto those of the LCC. A decision was made to exclude the CRDC's TOA and the SEO classifications. The advantages of their inclusion were not enough to justify the effort it would take to adapt them; moreover, the FOR functions well as a stand-alone classification system.

Using Excel's Find function, researchers used a bottom-up approach, starting with the most granular classification level in the LCC. For example, the lowest level of the LCC class, *Social Sciences: Industries. Land use. Labor: Land use: Real estate business* is "Real estate business," so a clear match was found within the CRDC Subclass *Social sciences: Economics and Business Administration: Economics: Real Estate Economics*. When a match was not possible on that level, the next highest level was looked at. For example, the LCC Class,

Geography. Anthropology. Recreation: Mathematical geography. Cartography: Cartography: Cadastral Mapping was mapped onto the CRDC's *Engineering and technology: Environmental Engineering and Related Engineering: Geomatics Engineering: Cartography*, since "Cadastral Mapping" is not a classification that exists within the CRDC. When no exact matches could be found, researchers manually searched through the FOR subject headings, starting with the broadest categories. If there was doubt about the meaning or use of a given LCC classification, researchers looked up journals listed under that classification on the DOAJ's website to provide context and content clues as to an appropriate classification within the CRDC system. Researchers also used Google as needed to define unfamiliar terms to aid in the classification process.

Findings

The CRDC was developed in a Canadian context specifically for use within the Research and Development domain and this worldview is reflected in the arrangement and vocabulary used in the FOR classification system. That said, the FOR system offers broad coverage in a variety of disciplines and subjects and, in most cases, its granular vocabulary allowed a migration from the LCC with relative ease. There were, however, occasions in which multiple CRDC classifications were used to accommodate the breadth and specificity of a particular LCC classification. There were additional cases where the CRDC vocabulary was overly precise, complicating attempts to find an equivalent match for LCC classifications with a broader scope, and other occasions in which no equivalent match could be found.

The LCC heading *Philosophy. Psychology. Religion.* provides an example of a subject which was classified as the best fit in the CRDC. A text about Buddhism, for example, would be classified within the LCC system under *Philosophy. Psychology. Religion: Buddhism.* The

CRDC, on the other hand, can only go as far as *Humanities and the Arts: History Archaeology and Related Studies*, *History Archaeology and Related Studies: Religion and Religious Studies: Eastern Religions*, thus losing a layer of specificity in the migration process. This demonstrates how some LCC headings may need to be placed under a CRDC heading which has a different chain of relation than the current classification system, which may not be as specific.

Further, there were instances in which the extreme specificity of the CRDC did not mesh well with broad headings within the LCC, and the LCC headings needed to be divided. For example, the LCC classification *Science: Physics: Nuclear and particle physics. Atomic energy. Radioactivity* covers multiple broad topics under one heading. The CRDC breaks particle physics and nuclear physics into two separate categories; however, radioactivity has a relationship with both. This degree of minutiae was also seen when attempting to migrate the LCC class *Science: Geology: Petrology*. Within the CRDC, petrology is split into three Subclasses: igneous petrology, metamorphic petrology, and ore deposit petrology. These examples demonstrate how some LCC classification will need to be divided into multiple CRDC Classes or Subclasses in order to be accommodated most correctly. The re-classification of affected DOAJ journals will have to be done on a case-by-case basis.

Another issue encountered during the mapping process was a lack of diversity within some areas of the CRDC. In the domain of history, the LCC offers a full four major divisions devoted to the topic: (C) Auxiliary Sciences of History; (D) World History and History and Europe; as well as (E and F) History of the Americas. The CRDC offers the Group *History, Archaeology and Related Studies* under the Division heading of *Humanities and Arts*. While this Group does contain a number of Subclasses, its regions are painted with broad strokes and what specificity it does have is more suitable to a Canadian context. The LCC, even with its

American-centric worldview, does a better job of granularity in this aspect. There are similar issues with Languages, Literature, and Law. However, other Divisions such as Engineering and technology did not experience this same Canadian bias.

In some cases, the lack of a specific Subclass within the CRDC could be addressed by using the “n.e.c” (not elsewhere classified) Subclass. For example, the LCC classification *Technology: Chemical technology: Explosives and pyrotechnics* was migrated to *Engineering and Technology: Chemical Engineering: Chemical Engineering: Chemical Engineering, n.e.c..* While it is not an exact fit, this “n.e.c” classification represents the best fit for this topic found in the CRDC.

Infrequently, the mapping process resulted in zero applicable or equivalent classifications, meaning that the LCC classification in question was not represented in any capacity by a heading in the CRDC system. Most notably, the LCC subject heading *General Works* and its subordinate classes had no CRDC corollary. Although this category does not represent a large proportion of journals in the DOAJ database, as the DOAJ deals primarily with research publications, any journal placed under this heading would have to be dealt with on a case-by-case basis.

Also of note is the fact that the DOAJ indexes journals in multiple classes, which allowed for flexibility in cases where a clean match was not found for a given LCC classification, essentially providing a secondary “back-up” classification to work with for the majority of journals.

Overall, the CRDC is a relatively comprehensive multi-disciplinary system, allowing a significant level of specificity and flexibility within its classifications. Within the sphere of Canadian Research and Development, it goes broad and deep. However, it was not created as a

universal system and as such, certain deficiencies were noted regarding a clean migration from the LCC to the CRDC.

The overall results are as follows: a straightforward one-to-one equivalence was achieved in 69% of the classifications, 23% of the classifications were placed into a best fit or n.e.c. Subclass, and 8% of the classifications were incompatible with the CRDC (figure 6). While the CRDC can accommodate the vast majority of the LCC classifications, a process of manual adaptation will need to be adopted in certain circumstances, likely at the journal level. While that does represent additional labour, it also may positively impact the search experience for the user by improving the precision with which journals are indexed.

Within the context of the research carried out for this evaluation, the process of finding appropriate mapping destinations by browsing the FOR subject headings had both benefits and drawbacks. While the process allowed our researchers to become more familiar with the CRDC system, it was time-consuming and subject to human error. The DOAJ may have a similar experience. Emphasis should be placed, however, on the fact that 69% of the classifications were easily migrated. An automated process could be applied to these simpler translations, freeing up time and energy to focus on the more complex cases. Compared to the LCC, the CRDC offers a more nuanced vocabulary which will increase the accuracy with which the journals in the DOAJ database may be classified and searched.

Figure 6*Percentage Of Mapped Classifications*

Note. This graph describes which percentage of LCC headings were classified onto the CRDC successfully, with a best fit, and which were unclassifiable.

Analysis of the New Classification System

In addition to the findings of the mapping process, an examination of the CRDC itself led to further conclusions about its structure and characteristics. We found that despite the breadth of the FOR classes, most of the available Classes or Subclasses were not used in the mapping process. Of 1669 full headings available in the CRDC FOR, only 374 were actually used. These unused headings provide new opportunities for classification, particularly for future journals.

Additionally, the CRDC provides a much more modern view of scholarship compared to the 2012 version of the LCC. For example, the CRDC recognizes philosophy and psychology as sufficiently distinct disciplines to put them in two separate classifications; whereas the LCC

groups them together in *Philosophy. Psychology. Religion*. The CRDC also recognizes new disciplines that the outdated LCC has trouble accommodating, for example: sexology, disability studies, and gender studies.

Overall, the system is well organized, easy to read, and to use for resource retrieval. The hierarchical system of Divisions, Groups, Classes and Subclasses means that users have many possible entry points to a topic. One could conduct a bottom-up or top-down search, both of which were tested during our mapping process.

One potential reason for issues with correlating LCC headings to CRDC headings may be related to the CRDC's focus on R&D related priorities in its classification design. The CRDC emphasises that there are multiple activities which may be associated with R&D which are not technically included within its definition of research as strictly investigative work. This distinction and the choice to exclude certain topics from being categorised as R&D means that the CRDC system is inherently designed to exclude certain topics. These exclusions are many and include, for example:

1. Education and training of personnel and students. While postgraduate research, and development of new teaching methods are included, teaching and training of students or personnel using established methods is not.
2. Specialized medical care and clinical trials, unless related to the development of new treatments and procedures, or scientific and technological advances.
3. Routine software development, and routine data collection. Unless it leads to an advance in the area of computer software.

Other activities may be excluded if they are considered ancillary or inconsequential to R&D (Statistics Canada, 2022a). These exclusions may lead to issues with the CRDC system, as

DOAJ journals are likely to include information on these topics. As they may not find an appropriate fit in the existing CRDC system, some FOR headings may need to be expanded to accommodate journals which would have otherwise been excluded.

However, the DOAJ's generally adaptable nature, its breadth, and its modern point of view ensure that it could be used to accurately classify emerging research. With some modification, the CRDC's focus on research, broad subject areas, and granular hierarchy make it well suited for classifying research journals in the DOAJ's collection.

Recommendations

Based on our analysis of the CRDC system and our evaluation of the mapping process, it is our recommendation that the DOAJ should consider adopting the CRDC classification system as a replacement for the LCC system. Although several adjustments would need to be made to the CRDC and the DOAJ's existing system to ensure that the new system functions smoothly and meets the DOAJ's requirements, we believe that the work would be well worth it. The following sections outline several recommendations with regards to each of the requirements the DOAJ has identified for an ideal alternative system, as well as the steps required to migrate from the LCC to the CRDC.

Easy for Humans to Use

The CRDC is generally intuitive, and for this reason, we believe that it meets the first of the DOAJ's requirements, namely, that the new system be easy for humans to use. It functions well both for employees classifying journals and for users doing research on the DOAJ website. The first three hierarchical levels of the FOR classifications are quite user-friendly, which means that amateurs and non-specialists can readily understand the scope and context of the terms used.

While the higher level FOR classifications facilitates more general searches, the Subclass headings use more granular terms which may appeal to specialists using the DOAJ.

Although the CRDC system pairs well with the DOAJ's existing search function, and the classification hierarchy and terminology should allow for easy source retrieval, the DOAJ's existing search interface could be improved to optimize resource retrieval in the CRDC system. At the search level, the addition of a toggle function with an option to explode hierarchy levels would allow the DOAJ to take full advantage of the CRDC's hierarchy. This would allow users the option to view only the selected Subclass, or to expand the results to include all the works classified in classification levels above the Subclass in question. For example, a user searching "RDF6010105" should be able to see *only* journals in that specific Subclass or choose also to see works classified in higher levels above that Subclass. In order to further maximize the useability of the FOR subject headings, we also recommend that the DOAJ develop a thesaurus. This could contain subject-heading translations to make terms more useful to an international audience. Ideally, the online search interface would be programmed to recognize synonyms and equate them with cardinal terms when carrying out searches.

Easy for Machines to Read

Both the CRDC and the LCC use alphanumeric classification codes, meaning that the CRDC meets the DOAJ's second requirement that a new system be easy for machines to read when processing metadata. At every level of the FOR hierarchy, each subject-heading is associated with an alphanumeric code. Regarding the transition from the LCC to CRDC, our mapping process associated 92% of the LCC codes in the DOAJ database with an equivalent CRDC code, so the majority of journals already classified in the DOAJ can be automatically re-classified, as this data can be exported in CSV.

While our researchers were able to map 92% of the existing LCC classifications onto an equivalent in the CRDC system, we were unable to find an applicable match for 8% of the existing LCC classifications. In quantifiable terms, this means that of the 496 unique LCC headings evaluated, 43 LCC notations were not matched to a CRDC notation. In the DOAJ database, these 43 notations are used to classify 1022 journals. In order to migrate from LCC to the CRDC, DOAJ classifiers would need to go through these 1022 journals and manually reclassify those with no secondary classification (an additional LCC classification that was successfully mapped onto the CRDC) or those with exclusively un-mapped classifications. Our researchers also found that current LCC indexing on the DOAJ database was inconsistent at times, which made the mapping process difficult in certain cases. For this reason, we make the additional recommendation that, after adopting the CRDC system, the DOAJ gradually go through already classified journals to ensure that there is a precise classification in every case.

Reflects DOAJ's International Multi-Lingual Scope

While the CRDC was designed with the intention of accommodating international research standards, in its current configuration, subject headings are only available in English and French. CRDC subject headings would have to be translated into multiple languages to better reflect the DOAJ's international and multilingual scope. Additionally, there are several Subclasses, primarily regarding literature, that reflect the CRDC's Canadian worldview. These include the following classifications: *Studies related to the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada*, *Canadian literatures in English*, *Quebec literatures*, and *Literatures in French outside Quebec*. If the DOAJ were to adopt the CRDC system, these Canadian Subclasses would need to be adjusted, updated, or replaced to better fit their international coverage.

Adaptable and Extendible

The CRDC has the additional benefit of hospitality and, consequently, it meets the DOAJ's criteria for adaptability and extendibility. The CRDC could be adapted to add new sections by extending alphanumeric codes. Each collection of Subclasses under any given Class terminates at an n.e.c. Subclass, numerically represented by RDF#####99. This leaves ample space between the last classification and RDF#####98 for expansion. For example, if the DOAJ needed an additional section on the topic of law, this could be accommodated with the new code of RDF5050126 (as the last code within this class is RDF5050125). This 10-character formula can be followed all the way to RDF5051298. If the DOAJ found that more Subclasses were required to meet their needs, they could start using decimals, or extend the codes to 11+ characters, allowing codes like RDF#####100, RDF#####101, etc.

The CRDC describes itself as a flexible classification system which was designed with multi-disciplinary research in mind. The CRDC recommends using multiple FOR headings when research is multidisciplinary or represents an emerging field. The hierarchical structure of FOR classifications enables research to potentially be applied across multiple Classes or Groups. Several areas of FOR can also be brought together using the secondary systems of the SEO. However, the implementation of the SEO as a secondary classification may need to be adapted for the DOAJ's requirements and is not specifically accounted for in this report. The CRDC also suggests aggregating various areas of the FOR under one definition if a topic needs to fit into multiple categories (Statistics Canada, 2020a), which may be a process the DOAJ can take into consideration to adapt this system to work well for them.

The CRDC system's focus on R&D's may be limiting for the DOAJ, as it explicitly excludes some topics which may be useful for the DOAJ. The CRDC's definitions of R&D topics may need to be adapted to address a broader selection of journals as they incorporate more

topics of research. However, this focus on research does align with the DOAJ's focus on indexing academic research journals and provides a good framework for the majority of the LCC classifications explored during the mapping process, so may not restrict the DOAJ much. It may be further noted that reviews of the CRDC are scheduled to be completed every two years, which could potentially relieve the DOAJ of some of the burden of upkeep as the CRDC will update itself with new areas of research over time.

Open Source

The CRDC's TOA, FOR and SEO structures and Divisions, Group, Class and Subclass descriptions are available on Canada.ca, and the system has an open government license (Treasury Board Secretariat, 2020), making it suitable for the DOAJ's preference of an open-source system.

Conclusions

First and foremost, much credit goes to the DOAJ. Built from the ground up and powered primarily by dedicated volunteers, they have created a site which is true to the ideals of open access to quality information. They have provided a user-friendly, high-quality index which is attractive to both journal creators and journal readers. In a world where even knowledge has been monetised, this is no small feat, and we would like to take this opportunity to recognize their continued efforts and success.

It is, in fact, due to this success that the DOAJ is looking for a classification system to replace the 2012 version of the LCC which they are currently using. In order to accommodate the growing number of diverse journals, the DOAJ is searching for a broader multi-faceted system which should be easily readable by both humans and machines, multi-lingual, adaptable and extendible, and open source. The Canadian Research and Development Classification meets

nearly all of these qualifications, with one exception being that it is not multi-lingual beyond English and French. Based on our research and findings, we recommend that the DOAJ consider the CRDC as a replacement for the LCC.

By manually mapping the existing LCC system onto the CRDC, we found that the majority (69%) of current classifications were easily migrated with an exact match to the CRDC, and 23% could be migrated with a “best-fit” approach. Only 8% of the classifications had no equivalent CRDC classification and would require manual consideration on a journal level. While it is true that both the “best-fit” and the “manual reclassification” cases would require an initial outlay of labour, we felt that the benefits of the CRDC made it worth the time. In addition to meeting nearly all the specifications of the DOAJ, the CRDC is a relatively comprehensive classification universe. It has the advantage of being both wide and deep - providing multiple classification options which will allow for greater search flexibility. It is not only adaptable and extendible; it is scheduled to be updated biannually by Statistics Canada, potentially reducing the DOAJ’s work in this regard. All things considered, we felt that the CRDC is a strong contender as a replacement classification system for the DOAJ.

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